

A Comparative analysis of Cybercrime Awareness among the Adolescents

Chetan U. Chavan, Shobha J. Gaddam

C. U. Chavan is an Associate Professor and Ph.D Research Guide from Gokhale Education Society's, College of Education and Research, Parel, Mumbai - 400012. University of Mumbai
S. J. Gaddam is a Ph.D. Research Scholar from University of Mumbai

ABSTRACT

The study is undertaken to find out the actual level of Cyber Crime Awareness among the Adolescents in Badlapur city of Thane District. For this purpose 100 Adolescents students studying in Standard Ninth following Maharashtra state board pattern were selected by Convenience Sampling Technique from the schools located in Badlapur. For the study 50 Adolescents from English medium school and 50 Adolescents from Marathi medium schools were chosen. The study was conducted by adopting the **Descriptive Survey Method** of research using **Cyber Crime Awareness Scale by Rajasekar S (CCAS-RS) tool**. The research findings of the study shows that there is a significantly great observable difference towards the cybercrime awareness among adolescents with respect to the medium of the instruction imparted in the school. In general, adolescents from English medium schools showed **Moderate awareness** on cybercrime awareness whereas comparatively the adolescents from Marathi medium schools showed **High awareness** on cybercrime awareness. The level of awareness was significantly found to be the same among the adolescent Boys as well as Girls of English medium schools. But the researcher found a significantly high level of awareness among the adolescent girls as compared to the adolescent boys of Marathi medium school. As adolescents are at a higher risk of becoming victims to the different forms of cyber crimes so a proper awareness and training programme should be rendered to them.

Keywords:

Adolescents, Cyber Crime, Awareness, CCAS- RS tool, Descriptive Survey, Maharashtra

1. INTRODUCTION

Cybercrime, by definition, is the criminal activity that either targets or uses a computer device. Cyber crime is a crucially rising problem which affects adolescents and young people. Knowingly or unknowingly, nearly 60% of adolescents are estimated to be involved in cybercrime. (Ahmad Waziri, 2019). The Over exposure to increased dependability on the use of the internet has led to the rise of cybercrime among the adolescent. The Internet offers multiple benefits to society, it presents attractive opportunities for crime by the use of new and highly sophisticated technological tools. (Aneeta Joshi and Sonali Kandpal, 2020). The present generations are drastically affected by cybercrime as they are less aware of the security available on the net (Deepa Swamy, 2018). The increase in the incidence of crimes and the emergence of new variants of cyber crimes pose greater challenges for legal and law enforcement (Urmila Goel, 2014)

2. NEED OF THE STUDY

The rise in the use of the Internet and the different computer online applications has subjected 21st century adolescents to a greater risk over the use of online social platforms. Online

schooling during the COVID pandemic has not only brought a big gap in the learning outcomes of the adolescent but has also affected the mental and social well-being of the adolescent. Everyone is very much dependent on the cyber world which also increases the space for cybercrime.

The researchers therefore feels that the present research is much needed due to the following factors:

1. Understanding the probable level of risk the adolescents are involved in by using and sharing information on social networking platforms
2. Knowing the level of awareness in protecting personal information and personal data.
3. Knowing the level of awareness for having a protective monetary transaction.
4. Checking the general awareness level among adolescents on different ways of cybercrime.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem that this study addresses is the identification of the actual level of awareness on cyber security among the adolescent students due to the present overexposure to the different technological advances leading to the ever increasing rise in cyber crimes and training them with the cyber security

awareness program is the only possible solution for solving this problem.

4. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Joshi Aneeta, Kandpal Sonali (2020) has found that there is no significant difference towards the cybercrime awareness among adolescents with respect to their gender and locality. However, urban adolescents have shown more familiarity on many cybercrime terms as compared to their rural counterparts.

Kumar Rajender (2020) has found a significant difference between Cyber-crime Awareness of male and female students and significant difference between Cyber-crime Awareness of rural and urban students. Male and urban students have more digital wrongdoing mindfulness than female and rural students.

Isma Rafiq (2020) The results of the study indicates that there is a significant difference between male and female adolescents on their level of cybercrime awareness. Male adolescents were observed with a high level of cyber crime awareness as compared to female adolescents.

Firdous Ahmad (2019) has found a significant difference between male and female adolescents on their level of cybercrime awareness. Male adolescents were observed with a high level of cybercrime awareness as compared to female adolescents.

Swamy Deepa (2018) has found that most of the teenagers do cyber crime without knowledge. Results indicated that teenagers using the internet have less knowledge about cyber crime.

Yang, Y., Zhou, L., Peng, Z., Using, S., Spread, N., Deng, S., & Huang, H. (2017). Likewise, students from Tamil Nadu India were surveyed to identify how aware are they on various security threat, the result indicated a total number of 500 students participated in the survey, 70% are aware of basic virus attacks and they are using anti-virus, and 11% uses outdated antivirus, also more than 97% uses free available antivirus online.

Tirumala, S. S., Sarrafzadeh, A., & Pang, P. (2016). Similarly from New Zealand, a cybersecurity awareness survey was conducted on the use of the internet among students of various ages, the final results show that the students are not familiar with the term phishing and other cybersecurity terms, and this revealed lack of knowledge in cybersecurity.

5. AIM OF THE STUDY

Analyzing the Cyber security awareness level among the adolescents based on the medium of instructions imparted in the school.

6. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To check the level of cyber crime awareness among the adolescents of standard ninth based on the medium of instructions imparted in the school.
2. To compare the level of cyber crime awareness among the adolescent boys and girls of standard ninth based on the medium of instructions imparted in the school.

7. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. DIRECTIONAL HYPOTHESIS:

There is a significant difference in the level of cyber crime awareness among the adolescent boys and girls of standard ninth based on the medium of instructions imparted in the school.

2. NULL HYPOTHESIS:

There is no significant difference in the level of cyber crime awareness among the adolescent boys and girls of standard ninth based on the medium of instructions imparted in the school.

8. DESIGN OF THE STUDY

8.1 Research Methodology:

Descriptive Survey Method of research was used.

8.2 Tool Used:

Cyber Crime Awareness Scale by Rajasekar S (CCAS-RS)
Tool

8.3 Research Question:

The following question will be answered at the end of the study.

1. What is the actual level of cyber security awareness among the adolescent boys and girls based on the medium of instructions imparted in the school?

8.4 Population:

For the present study the adolescent students of standard 9 in the Ambernath tehsil of Badlapur city of thane district of Maharashtra state following the SSC board syllabus was chosen.

8.5 Sample:

Maharashtra State Board English medium as well as Marathi medium Schools situated in the West and East Zone of Badlapur city of Thane District

8.6 Sample Size:

Total no. of students studied - 100

8.7 Sampling Technique:

Convenience Sampling Technique was used.

9. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the survey conducted, the following result were obtained

Table 1: Interpretation of Cybercrime Awareness for English Medium Schools

Scores	No. of Students	Interpretation
143 & Above	4	Excellent Awareness
133 - 142	5	High Awareness
123 - 132	5	Above Average Awareness
108 - 122	24	Moderate Awareness
99 - 107	8	Below Average Awareness
80 - 98	4	Low Awareness

Table 1 reveals the Mean scores scored by the 50 Adolescents of English Medium Schools involved in the study. From the table, it is noticed that the majority of adolescents have Moderate awareness to Below Average awareness about Cyber crime.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of Cybercrime Awareness among the Adolescents of English Medium Schools in Thane District.

Table 2: Interpretation of Cybercrime Awareness for Marathi Medium Schools

Scores	No. of Students	Interpretation
143 & Above	12	Excellent Awareness
133 - 142	20	High Awareness
123 - 132	2	Above Average Awareness
108 - 122	8	Moderate Awareness
99 - 107	5	Below Average Awareness
80 - 98	3	Low Awareness

Table 2 reveals the Mean scores scored by the 50 Adolescents of Marathi Medium Schools involved in the study. From the table, it is noticed that the majority of adolescents have High awareness to Excellent awareness about Cyber crime.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of Cybercrime Awareness among the Adolescents of Marathi Medium Schools in Thane District.

Table 3: Level of Cyber Crime Awareness Of Adolescents

Variables (Medium of Instruction)	Cyber Crime Awareness			T - Value	Significant Level
	N	Mean	SD		
English	50	109	7.864	0.0001	Significant
Marathi	50	140.36	15.304		

Table 3 reveals that the mean scores of adolescents of Marathi medium school is 140.36 which is higher than the mean score of adolescents of English medium school which is 109. It means that the adolescents from Marathi medium schools have high awareness towards cybercrime as compared to the adolescents of English medium schools. **The t-value is 0.0001 hence, by conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be extremely statistically significant** at 0.05 level of significance. **Hence, the Null Hypothesis** “There is no significant difference in the level of cyber crime awareness among the adolescent boys and girls of standard ninth based on the medium of instructions imparted in the school” **is rejected**. Hence, Cybercrime awareness is affected by medium of instructions.

Figure 3: Graphical representation for Comparison of Cybercrime Awareness

10. CONCLUSION

The 100 Adolescents of Standard Ninth who underwent the survey reveals that the **50 Adolescents of Marathi medium school are having HIGH AWARENESS as compared to the 50 Adolescents of English medium school**. The researcher found out that the adolescents of the English medium schools showed **Moderate awareness** in terms of the negative questions present in the research tool. A deep study

about cybercrime awareness is needed with the large sample in order for the researcher to develop an appropriate programme for Cyber Security among the Adolescents.

The level of awareness was significantly found to be the same among the Boys as well as Girls. Instead, **the individual scores of Girls of Marathi medium schools revealed that Girls possessed Excellent Awareness as compared to Boys**. Hence, a proper training or cyber security awareness programme must be conducted among the students to make them aware of the cyber crimes happening among them and the right approach to stay out of it.

11. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The present study can be useful for the school and college teachers as well as students. It will help the teachers to know the level of awareness of cybercrime in students of different age groups and medium of instruction additionally guide them about the harmful effects of using the internet without the use of proper preventive measures. In this way students can protect themselves from the different cyber crimes and attacks that they might fall prey to knowingly or unknowingly while surfing the internet and social networking sites.

12. REFERENCES

Swamy Deepa “Awareness of Cyber Crime Among Teenagers” Int J Recent Sci Res. 9(5),pp.27073-27075. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.24327/ijrsr.2018.0905.2182> 2018

Goel, Urmila “Awareness among B. Ed teacher training towards cyber-crime- A study, Learning Community”, Vol. 5 (2), August 2014, pp.107-117

Waziri Ahmad, “Cyber Crime Among Adolescents” - University of Sunderland, Academia. Edu, December 2019. [https://www.academia.edu/42099969/CYBER_CRIME_AMONG_A DOLESCENTS](https://www.academia.edu/42099969/CYBER_CRIME_AMONG_A_DOLESCENTS)

Firdous Ahmad, ‘CYBERCRIME AWARENESS AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN DISTRICT KUPWARA OF NORTH KASHMIR’. Journal Current Science. ISSN: 9726 - 001X, Impact Factor: 5.97 Vol. 20, No 06 2019

Kumar Rajender ‘A Study of Cyber Crime Awareness Among B.Ed. And M.Ed. Students of Sirsa District.’ International Economic Society. Volume 11, Issue 3, PP. 74-86. 2020

Joshi Aneeta ‘Cyber Crime Awareness among the Adolescents’, International Journal of creative research thoughts, volume 8 Issue 12 December 2020, pp 1737-1743. 2020

Isma Rafiq, ‘An analytical study of cybercrime awareness among adolescents of district Srinagar.’ Int J Adv Acad Stud 2020;2(3):489-492. DOI: 10.33545/27068919.2020.v2.i3g.194. 2020

Tirumala,S.S., Sarrafzadeh, A., ‘A survey on internet usage and cybersecurity awareness in students.’ December 2016,DOI:10.1109/PST.2016.7906931

AUTHORS

Chetan Uttamrao Chavan is working as an Associate Professor in Gokhale Education Society's College of Education and Research, Parel, Mumbai, Affiliated to University of Mumbai. He is an educationalist by training and experience. He has been in the field of education for more than 17 years. He has obtained his Master of Science (Physics) and M.A.(Psychology), M.Ed, D.S.M,SET, NET, Ph.D. in Education. He is a recognised guide for Ph.D in Education from University of Mumbai. He has published many research papers and articles in different State, National, International level journals.

Shobha Joy Gaddam is a Ph.D. Research Scholar from University of Mumbai. She is an Academician and Educator by profession. She holds a Masters in Science (Biotechnology), M.A. Education, CIG (Certificate in Guidance), B.Ed and PGDSL.M. Being a school principal she is keenly interested in bringing technological and educational awareness among the adolescents. She loves to create self help blogs, short articles, Quotes, educational videos for teacher educators and pupils. Her areas of expertise include school management and leadership. She enjoys horticulture and gardening as her special interest.